

Effect of Gamma Radiation on the Drug Release Mechanism from Poly(vinyl) Alcohol Gel Nanocarriers

Wanis Nafo^{1,*}

¹ School of Physics, University of Galway, Galway, University Road, Galway, H91 CF50, Ireland.

* Corresponding Author: wanis.nafo@universityofgalway.ie; ORCID: 0000-0001-8320-2422.

1. Objective

This study aims to investigate the effect of gamma irradiation on the drug release kinetics of protein-loaded poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA) hydrogel nanoparticles synthesized via a freeze–thaw emulsification method. Specifically, we examine how varying doses of gamma radiation, spanning a clinically relevant range (0–80 Gy), influence the structural integrity of the hydrogel matrix and modulate the release behavior of a model protein drug (BSA). By integrating cumulative release assays with FTIR spectroscopy, the work seeks to elucidate the underlying mechanisms, crosslinking versus degradation, that govern the radiation-responsive performance of PVA-based nanocarriers. The findings provide insight into the potential of gamma irradiation as a tunable stimulus for controlled drug delivery applications, particularly in oncology settings where radiation is already part of standard therapeutic regimens.

2. Preparation of gel nanocarriers

2.1. Materials:

Poly(vinyl alcohol) (PVA, average molecular weight ~89,000–98,000, 99+% hydrolyzed; Product No. 378321) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA). Bovine serum albumin (BSA, lyophilized powder, ≥96%; Product No. 810533) and silicone oil (viscosity: 350 cSt; Product No. 341584) were also obtained from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA).

2.2. Preparation of PVA hydrogel nanoparticles

PVA (1,667 mg) was dissolved in 10 ml of phosphate buffer (20 mM, pH 7.4) by heating at approximately 100 °C for 15 minutes. The solution was then cooled to room temperature. In parallel, BSA (417 mg) was dissolved in 6.67 ml of the same phosphate buffer at room temperature. The two solutions were then thoroughly mixed to form a homogeneous aqueous phase. This mixture was added to 35 ml of silicone oil and subjected to ultrasonication (Sonicator Model: Fisherbrand™ Q125, Thermo Fisher Scientific) at an amplitude of 30 with 5-second on/off pulses for 5 minutes to generate a water-in-oil (w/o) emulsion.

The resulting emulsion was frozen at –20 °C for 20 hours and subsequently thawed at room temperature for 4 hours. This single freeze–thaw cycle led to the formation of a suspension of PVA hydrogel nanoparticles in silicone oil. To extract the nanoparticles, acetone equal in volume to the silicone oil (35 ml) was added (1:1 v/v), and the mixture was filtered through a filter membrane (Altman, 1.1 μm pore size). The filtrate was then washed with acetone to remove any residual silicone oil. Finally, the collected PVA hydrogel nanoparticles were vacuum-dried and stored at 4 °C for further analysis. The produced nanocarriers are considered matrix-based nano-systems [1]

Figure 1. Phase separation: Acteon + PVA gel nanoparticles (top), silicon oil (bottom).

Figure 2. Produced nanoparticles.

2.3. Microscopic observation

Morphology of the dried PVA hydrogel nanoparticles was investigated by using a Hitachi scanning electron microscope (SEM, Hitachi, Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) regarding the shape and surface characteristics.

2.4. Determination of size and size distribution

BSA-loaded PVA hydrogel nanoparticles prepared using a single freeze–thaw cycle (4 mg) were suspended in 2 ml of DI water by gentle hand shaking. A 1 ml aliquot of the suspension was analyzed using a Litesizer™ particle analyzer (Anton Paar GmbH, Graz, Austria) to determine the intensity-weighted average particle size and size distribution. Measurements were performed on nanoparticles from five independent batches, and the reported particle size represents the average of these five determinations.

2.5. Measurement of protein loading efficiency

Dried PVA hydrogel nanoparticles (2 mg) were accurately weighed and transferred into test tubes. Phosphate buffer (3 ml, 20 mM, pH 7.4) was added to each tube, and the samples were incubated in a shaking water bath at 37 °C. After 48 hours of incubation, the samples were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 5 minutes. One milliliter of the resulting supernatant was carefully collected for protein quantification.

The concentration of BSA released into the supernatant was determined using the Bicinchoninic Acid (BCA) Protein Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), following the manufacturer's protocol. Absorbance measurements were performed at 562 nm using a Varioskan™ LUX Multimode Microplate Reader (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). A standard curve was constructed using known concentrations of BSA.

To correct for background absorbance, supernatant from blank PVA nanoparticles (prepared without BSA) was used as a control. The final BSA concentration was calculated by subtracting the absorbance of the blank sample from the test sample.

Protein loading efficiency was calculated using the following equation:

$$\text{Loading efficiency (\%)} = \frac{M_{\text{actual}}}{M_{\text{theoretical}}} \times 100$$

Where M_{actual} is the amount of BSA released and quantified from the nanoparticles, and $M_{\text{theoretical}}$ is the amount of BSA initially added during the nanoparticle preparation.

2.6. BSA Cumulative Release from PVA Hydrogel Nanoparticles

To assess the cumulative release of BSA, 2 mg of dried BSA-loaded PVA hydrogel nanoparticles were accurately weighed and transferred into sterile glass vials. Each vial was supplemented with 2 ml of phosphate buffer (20 mM, pH 7.4), and the nanoparticles were dispersed by ultrasonication for 3 minutes to ensure homogeneity. The samples were divided into six groups: non-irradiated control, and those exposed to gamma irradiation at doses of 5 Gy, 10 Gy, 20 Gy, 40 Gy, and 80 Gy using a calibrated Co-60 source.

All vials were incubated in a shaking water bath at 37 °C. At each predetermined time point (2 h, 5 h, 24 h, and 48 h), 0.9 ml of the supernatant was withdrawn and replaced with an equal volume of fresh phosphate buffer to maintain sink conditions. The collected aliquots were centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 5 minutes, and the supernatant was carefully collected for BSA quantification.

Protein concentration in the supernatant was determined using the BCA Protein Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), following the manufacturer's instructions. Absorbance was measured at 562 nm using the Microplate Reader. A standard calibration curve was constructed using known concentrations of BSA in phosphate buffer. To correct for background absorbance, supernatant from blank PVA nanoparticles (prepared without BSA) was used as a reference. The net BSA concentration was calculated by subtracting the absorbance of the blank from the test sample.

Cumulative release (%) was expressed as the ratio of the cumulative amount of BSA released at each time point to the total theoretical BSA content. All measurements were performed in triplicate.

2.7. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Spectroscopy

FTIR analysis was performed to assess potential structural changes in PVA hydrogel nanoparticles following gamma irradiation. For each group, non-irradiated, 5 Gy, 10 Gy, 20 Gy, and 40 Gy, 7 mg of dried nanoparticles were accurately weighed and placed in sterile glass vials. The samples were irradiated using a Co-60 gamma source at the designated doses.

Following irradiation, samples were analyzed using the Shimadzu IRSpirit™ FTIR Spectrophotometer equipped with a QATR-S single-reflection ATR accessory (Plastic Analyzer method package, Shimadzu, Singapore). Spectra were collected over the range of 4000–400 cm^{-1} with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , averaging 32 scans per sample. All spectra were baseline corrected and normalized prior to interpretation.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Morphology and shape

Figure 3 presents a scanning electron micrograph illustrating the morphology, size, and surface features of the PVA hydrogel nanoparticles. The particles exhibit a predominantly spherical shape. Surface roughness is also evident, which may be ascribed to shrinkage of the hydrogel matrix during the drying stage, as water evaporation can induce structural contraction.

Figure 3. A scanning electron micrograph of the PVA hydrogel nanoparticles showing the shape and the surface characteristics.

3.2. Size and size distribution

The size distribution of the PVA hydrogel nanoparticles follows a skewed, log-normal pattern, as illustrated in Figure 4. Based on five independent batch measurements, the intensity-weighted average diameter was determined to be 349.1 ± 10 nm. Several processing parameters were reported to significantly influence the final particle size. In particular, the volume ratio of the aqueous phase (comprising PVA and BSA in buffer) to the organic phase (silicone oil), the concentration of PVA in the aqueous phase, and the homogenization speed were identified as key determinants of particle size distribution [2]. Reducing the viscosity of the silicone oil in our study tangibly reduced the size of the nanoparticles.

Notably, no external emulsifier was used during nanoparticle preparation. Despite this, the water-in-oil emulsion demonstrated relative stability throughout the freeze–thaw cycle, with a slight phase separation once mixing stopped. This stability may be attributed to the thermal stability of the silicone oil, as well as the inherent surface-active properties of PVA, which has previously been reported to function as an emulsifier in microsphere formulations [3, 4]. Moreover, the freezing step at -20 °C likely contributed to emulsion stability by immobilizing the dispersed phase.

Figure 4. Intensity-weighted particle size distribution of the PVA hydrogel nanoparticles.

3.3. Protein loading efficiency

Protein loading efficiency was determined in triplicate. A notable advantage of the formulation and preparation method employed for the PVA hydrogel nanoparticles is the exceptionally high protein loading efficiency, reaching up to $92.5 \pm 2\%$. This high encapsulation efficiency is likely attributed to the use of silicone oil as the continuous phase during emulsification, in which the model protein, BSA, is poorly soluble. As a result, the majority of BSA molecules remain confined within the aqueous phase and are subsequently entrapped within the PVA hydrogel matrix during nanoparticle formation.

3.4. Effect of gamma irradiation on drug release

In this study, we systematically investigated the impact of gamma irradiation on drug release behavior and the molecular architecture of PVA-based nanoparticles, with irradiation doses spanning a therapeutic range from 0 Gy (control) to 80 Gy. This work aimed to elucidate the interplay between structural alterations in the polymer matrix and the resultant drug release kinetics, providing insight into the dual role of irradiation in modulating nanocarrier performance.

Drug release profiles under irradiation stress were monitored over 48 hours and are presented in Figure 6. The data show that gamma irradiation significantly modulates the cumulative release of the encapsulated drug. A reduced release rate is observed at a low dose of 5 Gy, where drug release plateaus at approximately 93%. This attenuation in release suggests that low-dose gamma exposure may induce additional physical crosslinking within the PVA matrix, restricting chain mobility and transiently impeding diffusion pathways. Interestingly, as the irradiation dose increases beyond this threshold, drug release not only returns to baseline (as observed in the non-irradiated control) but ultimately surpasses it. Specifically, at doses of 40 Gy and 80 Gy, cumulative release approaches or exceeds 100%, indicating a release-enhancing effect likely linked to radiation-induced degradation of the polymeric matrix.

Figure 5. Drug release profiles from nanocarriers subjected to different radiation

To corroborate these findings at the molecular level, FTIR was employed to monitor chemical structure changes across the dose spectrum (Figure 7). The spectral analysis of control samples confirmed characteristic absorption bands of PVA, including a broad peak between $3200\text{--}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to O–H stretching, and a C–H stretching band near 2900 cm^{-1} . Notably, the O–H band intensity diminishes following exposure to 5 Gy and 10 Gy, consistent with a reduction in available hydroxyl groups, likely due to enhanced hydrogen bonding and network densification associated with crosslinking.

Figure 6. Selected spectrum profiles for radiated PVA-gel NCs compared to pristine PVA-gel nanocarriers dosages.

Conversely, at higher doses (20 Gy–80 Gy), the FTIR spectra reveal marked alterations in the fingerprint region ($1100\text{--}1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$), including attenuation and peak shifts in bands corresponding to C=O, C=C, C–O, and C–N stretching vibrations. These observations are indicative of chain scission and oxidative degradation processes becoming dominant at elevated irradiation levels. The relatively stable C–H stretching band across all samples suggests that the polymer backbone retains its integrity at low to moderate doses, with degradation localized more prominently to functional side groups.

These complementary datasets suggest a dose-dependent dual mechanism governing drug release. At low doses, gamma irradiation acts primarily as a physical crosslinking agent, increasing matrix density and reducing diffusivity. However, with progressive dose escalation, chemical degradation supersedes crosslinking, leading to increased porosity and matrix relaxation that facilitates drug diffusion. The observed shift from restricted to enhanced release thus mirrors the transition from structural stabilization to degradation within the nanocarrier system.

Taken together, these findings highlight the potential of gamma irradiation as a tunable trigger for modulating nanocarrier performance. By carefully calibrating the irradiation dose, it is possible to balance crosslinking and degradation processes to achieve desired release kinetics. This strategy offers a promising avenue for designing radiation-responsive drug

delivery systems, particularly suited for localized therapy in oncology where irradiation is already an integral component of treatment.

4. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that gamma irradiation exerts a dose-dependent influence on both the structural properties and drug release behavior of BSA-loaded PVA hydrogel nanocarriers. Nanoparticles prepared via a freeze–thaw emulsification technique exhibited high encapsulation efficiency (~92.5%) and consistent morphology, with an average particle size around 349 nm. The cumulative release studies and FTIR spectral analysis collectively revealed a biphasic mechanism governing the release kinetics under varying gamma doses.

At lower doses (5–10 Gy), irradiation appears to promote additional crosslinking within the PVA network, reducing hydroxyl availability and limiting drug diffusion. This results in a modest suppression of release, as evidenced by reduced cumulative release values. However, as the dose increases beyond 20 Gy, gamma-induced bond scission and oxidative degradation begin to dominate. The resulting structural loosening and increased porosity of the matrix markedly enhance drug release, culminating in near-complete or even accelerated release at 40–80 Gy.

These findings underscore the dual role of gamma irradiation as both a stabilizing and destabilizing agent within the nanocarrier system. The ability to modulate drug release by controlling irradiation dose provides a valuable strategy for tailoring therapeutic profiles, especially in radiation-adjunct cancer therapies. Future studies may extend this work by exploring in vivo relevance, cytocompatibility under clinical dose rates, and tunability using alternative irradiation sources or polymer blends.

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